

Interaction between Copper Oxide and Neutral Salt Solutions.

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In a previous communication (Mukherjee and Iyer, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 307), the nature of the interface between copper oxide and the aqueous phase as deduced from electro-osmotic measurements was briefly discussed and conclusions were drawn from the experimental data regarding the interchange of ions between the double layer and the aqueous phase. The investigation of the reaction between systems like copper oxide and neutral salts is very interesting, in so far as such reactions can be interpreted from the two rival points of view. Mukherjee (*Presidential Address, Indian Science Congress*, 1929) has pointed out clearly experiments which decide definitely in favour of the Ion Adsorption Theory. The various physical and chemical properties of *interfaces* can be always determined by the nature of the *fixation* of ions at the interface. The variation of the electrical charge of copper oxide in contact with solutions of salts has been discussed in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*). In the present paper, the adsorption and liberation of alkali by copper oxide has been undertaken and the nature of the ion-exchanges taking place has been fully elucidated and the defects of the 'Chemical Theory' pointed out.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The purity of the sample of the copper oxide is of extreme importance in investigations of this type, where the amount of alkali liberated is of the order of 10^{-6} g. ions and hence very great care was taken in the preparation of the copper oxide. It was obtained by treating copper sulphate solution with a slight excess of sodium hydroxide in the hot condition and the precipitate was then washed for several days by decantation. When the sample as tested with the wash liquid was fairly free from alkali, it was subsequently subjected to a process of electro-dialysis using collodion membrane and

a 110 volt D.C. Conductivity water was employed for the purification of the substance. The purity of the substance finally obtained was found out by determining whether the conductivity of the wash liquid was identical with that of the water employed for washing. It was noticed that as the process of purification proceeded, the substance passed into the colloidal condition. The sample was finally dried in an air oven at 100°.

(A) *Liberation of alkali with electrolytes.*—The experimental technique employed for the measurement of alkalinity is much the same as that elaborated by Mukherjee and co-workers. (*cf. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 128, 3023; Ghosh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 128, 2605). Care was taken to see that the alkalinity developed was not due to the solution of the glass, by performing 'blank' experiments in similar Jena vessels.

TABLE I.

Alkali liberated with different electrolytes.

Copper oxide in contact with	pH.		pH.
(a) Pure water ...	6.6	(f) N-BaCl ₂ ...	9.4
(b) N-KCl ...	9.4	(g) .1 N-BaCl ₂ ...	9.1
(c) .1 N-KCl ...	9.0	(h) N-K ₂ SO ₄ ...	9.8
(d) N-NaCl ...	9.4	(i) N-Na ₂ SO ₄ ...	9.8
(e) .1 N-NaCl ...	9.0	(j) N-KNO ₃ ...	9.2
		(k) .1 N-KNO ₃ ...	9.0

It can be clearly seen from the above that there is a very close correlation between the development of alkali and the electrokinetic behaviour of the substance, as deduced from electro-omotic measurements cited in the previous paper. Two points are brought out very clearly.

(1) The nature of the cation employed has little influence on the amount of alkali liberated.

(2) The valency of the anion determines the alkalinity developed and follows the series SO₄' > Cl' > NO₃'.

(B) *Measurements of the alkali liberated from the sample of copper oxide.*—A known weight (10 g.) of the sample was taken in a Jena bottle and shaken up with 100 c.c. of N-KCl solution and

allowed to stand for 24 hours. The alkalinity developed was measured and after pipetting out carefully most of the supernatant liquid, another 100 c.c. of N-KCl was added and the same process was repeated from day to day. The following table gives the values obtained:—

TABLE II.

Total alkali liberated from copper oxide.

Copper oxide taken = 10 g.			Vol of N-KCl added = 100 c.c.		
Day.	p_H of supernatant liquid.		Day.	p_H of supernatant liquid.	
1st.	...	9.4	12th.	...	8.4
2nd.	...	9.4	13th.	...	8.2
3rd.	...	9.3	14th.	...	8.0
4th.	...	9.2	15th.	...	7.8
5th.	...	9.0	16th.	...	7.7
6th.	...	9.1	17th.	...	7.6
7th.	...	9.05	18th.	...	7.6
8th.	...	9.0	19th.	...	7.6
9th.	...	8.9	20th.	...	7.6
10th.	...	8.8	20th.—30th.	...	7.6
11th.	...	8.6			each day

From the above data, the total alkali liberated from one gram of copper oxide is found to be equal to 1.3904×10^{-6} g. ions per gram of the copper oxide.

The day-to-day measurement of the p_H of the liquid offers a very interesting evidence regarding the interchange of ions that takes place in the double layer as is pointed out in the discussion. It is also noticed that the colour of the precipitate changes appreciably during the final stages of the washing with KCl. Originally the copper oxide is dark in colour, but as the washing with potassium chloride proceeds, it gets a greenish tinge. Since the constant p_H of 7.6 was maintained for several days, and there was no indication of any fall in its value, attempts were made to find out the effect of washing the sample with water at this stage and it

was found that the p_{H} of the wash water was 6.2 for the first washing with 100 c.c. of water and 6.0 for the next 100 c.c. The washing was thus continued and considerable amounts of acid was thus liberated until finally the substance got back to the original colloidal condition, when the p_{H} also reached 6.8. Again the same process of liberation of alkali with neutral salts could be repeated.

(C) *Adsorption of alkalis by copper oxide.*—Experiments were performed to find out if the sample of pure copper oxide is capable of adsorbing alkali. The method adopted was based on the loss of conductivity of a very dilute solution of sodium or barium hydroxide, when it was shaken up with a given quantity of copper oxide. Allowance was made for the dilution which might be introduced by the moisture contained in the copper oxide. It is found that there is a distinct loss of conductance when the sample is shaken up with alkali. The amount of alkali adsorbed per g. of the sample = 1.12×10^{-6} g. ions. per gram of CuO.

Discussion.

In the previous paper (*loc. cit.*), it was suggested that the ions in primary layer must be assumed to be univalent, *i.e.*, cupric ions with a fixed hydroxyl ion forming the univalent positive unit, and hydroxyl ions equal in number forming the mobile sheet of the double layer. It is observed that the alkalinity developed is determined by the concentration of the electrolyte also, which is to be expected on the basis of the Ion Adsorption Theory.

The case of copper oxide, for which there is distinct evidence to show that it is dehydrated, differs from that of silica which is heavily hydrated. We may picture the interface, in the case of CuO, as consisting of solid particles on which, according to the views of Mukherjee, an excess of CuOH ions are fixed at certain points due to the operation of chemical valency forces and OH ions which go to form the mobile sheet of the double layer. According to this view, the formation of alkali may be represented by the reaction.

Thus the maximum amount of alkali liberated in the primary stage is determined by the number of hydroxyl ions in the mobile sheet of the double layer. Besides this primary reaction, a secondary one resulting in the replacement of a certain number CuOH^+ by CuCl^+ is possible and this would result in the net positive charge being increased. It should be noted that the replacement of OH in the primary layer is not so easy as in the secondary layer and is a slow process. This explains the constant p_{H} of 7.6 which continues for days together. The change in colour pointed out earlier is according to the 'Chemical Theory' due to the basic chloride being formed at the interface. The development of the acidity when the sample is treated with water can be represented by the reaction:

This explains the experimental result that we get back the original sample on repeatedly washing the above sample with water.

If we try to explain the liberation of alkali and the electrokinetic behaviour of copper oxide with potassium sulphate solution, we have to assume a series of chemical changes of the following type to take place as has been discussed by Mukherjee. (i) "At low concentrations, 'complex' cations containing alkali metal ions are formed such that the product of the free valencies and the additional complex ions is greater than that of the original non-diffusible ions, whose place they have taken or that the more dissociable copper sulphate molecules are formed on the surface." (ii) In the second place, the undissociated molecules of copper sulphate are formed resulting in the diminution of charge and liberation of alkali. (iii) At still higher concentrations we have to assume the formation of some complexes which get negatively charged. Simultaneously with the formation of basic anion, it is necessary to assume that the basic sulphate is also formed. When the concentration is still further increased, the degree of dissociation of the complex must still further diminish. Thus the 'Chemical Theory' imposes too many arbitrary assumptions and it is also difficult to see why the complexes remain fixed on the surface and why they are so readily formed with polyvalent ions of opposite sign. Then again, it is necessary to make suitable assumptions regarding

the solubility of these complexes. The difference between the ' Chemical Theory ' and the ' Adsorption Theory ' pointed herein, is that the chemical reactions, if they take place at all, must be confined in cases of this type to the surface layer and as such there cannot be any stoichiometric relationship.

Summary.

1. The liberation of alkali when highly purified copper oxide is shaken up with neutral salt solutions is closely connected with the electrokinetic behaviour of the substance in contact with solutions of different electrolytes. Just as the valency and mobility of the ' anion ' of the added electrolyte determines the electrical charge on the particles, so also the concentration of alkali liberated depends on the nature and concentration of the anion and not the cation.

2. The *primary* adsorption of hydroxyl ions by the sample of copper oxide has been proved by conductivity measurements.

3. The total quantity of alkali liberated from a given amount of the copper oxide by neutral salt solutions bears no stoichiometric relationship to the amount of substance taken.

4. The *Surface Dissociation Theory*, when applied to the system, CuO-neutral salt solutions, is found to be untenable, since it involves making too many arbitrary assumptions, while the *Adsorption Theory*, as put forward by Mukherjee, can explain the different sets of phenomena in a very satisfactory way.

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